

Carbon, Nitrogen and Sulphur Mineralisation in a Soil from Three Decomposing Plant Materials of Varying C/N, C/S and N/S Ratios

U. BHATTACHARJYA and PARTHA MUKHOPADHYAY

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswa Vidyalaya, Kalyani, West Bengal

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A laboratory incubation study was undertaken to compare the carbon, nitrogen and sulphur mineralisation in a soil from three decomposing plant materials, namely, dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*), cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*) and water-hyacinth (*Eichornia crassipes*) of varying C/N, C/S and N/S ratios applied at five different levels. Both carbon and nitrogen mineralisation from three different plant materials followed the order: dhaincha > cowpea > water-hyacinth. The extent of carbon mineralisation was found to be a reflection of the organic carbon content of the added organic matter. C/N ratio of the added plant material predominantly controls nitrogen mineralisation in soil. While sulphur mineralisation was found not only to depend on the sulphur content of the added plant material but also to their composition in relation to organic carbon and total nitrogen.

ADDITION of plant residue to supplement N, P, S and other nutrient requirements of crops is usually included in the management practices of cultivated soils. Most of the nitrogen and sulphur in soil are present in organic form and plants are largely dependent upon the mineralisation of nitrogen and sulphur from the native or added organic matter in soil.

Since carbon, nitrogen and sulphur exist in close relationship in soil organic matter, many workers are of opinion that their mineralisation would be similar (Walker¹; Bardsley and Lancaster²). But Hesse³ failed to observe sulphur mineralisation in soil where appreciable amounts of carbon and nitrogen were mineralised. Barrow⁴ concluded that mineralisation of added organic matter depends on its sulphur content in much the same way as the mineralisation of nitrogen depends on nitrogen content. Mukhopadhyay⁵ observed that the amount of sulphur mineralised from added organic matter was closely related to the sulphur content rather than its C/S ratio. In view of the inconsistencies in the results, the present study was undertaken to investigate the relative effects of three different types of plant materials of varying C/N, C/S and N/S ratios on mineralisation of carbon, nitrogen and sulphur in soil.

Experimental

The experiment was conducted with a soil (0-15 cm layer) collected from Kalyani in Nadia district of West Bengal.

The pH, organic C%, total N%, CEC (mg/100 g), water holding capacity, available nitrogen (NH_4^+ NO_3^- in mg/100 g) and available sulphate sulphur (0.15% CaCl_2 extractable in mg/100 g) contents of

the soil are 8.4, 0.27, 0.03, 9.1, 31.8, 39.1 and 38.1 respectively.

The oven dried plant samples used in the present study were dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) leaves, vegetative parts of cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*) and water-hyacinth (*Eichornia crassipes*) with 36.45, 36.03 and 29.97% carbon, 3.64, 2.80 and 2.0% nitrogen and 0.431, 0.462 and 0.212% sulphur respectively.

Besides control, where no source of organic matter was added, treatments with respect to each of the above material samples were added separately @ 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5% of the soil.

For each of the above treatments duplicate samples of 10 g soil were taken in a series of glass tubes (size 15 cm x 2.5 cm) and the requisite quantities of treatment materials were separately mixed with the soil and incubated for 6 weeks maintaining moisture levels corresponding to 50% of the moisture holding capacity of the soil. Separate sets were maintained for monitoring the changes in the mineralisation of carbon, nitrogen and sulphur. Three tubes were placed inside an Erlenmeyer flask of 1 litre capacity together with a tube containing a known concentration of NaOH solution for estimating the amount of CO_2 evolved during the incubation period. A few ml of water was placed in the flask to maintain high humidity⁶. The flask was closed and incubated at laboratory room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$) for 6 weeks.

Available nitrogen was determined following the method of Hesse⁷ after extracting the soil with 2M KCl solution. Available sulphate sulphur was determined following the reduction method of Johnson and Nishita⁸ after extracting the soil with 0.15% CaCl_2 solution (Soil : Solution ratio 1 : 2.5).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PLANT MATERIALS ADDITION ON MINERALISATION OF CARBON, NITROGEN AND SULPHUR IN SOIL

Level of addition	Type of plant material	Carbon		Available nitrogen		Available sulphur	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
0.5%	Cowpea	387.6	210.7	41.6	- 5.2	6.2	-51.8
	Waterhyacinth	234.0	57.1	33.8	-13.0	78.6	20.6
	Dhaincha	434.0	257.1	52.0	5.2	25.0	-33.0
1.0%	Cowpea	431.5	254.6	52.0	5.2	34.3	-23.7
	Waterhyacinth	357.3	180.4	33.8	-13.0	3.1	-54.9
	Dhaincha	466.8	289.9	96.3	49.5	28.1	-29.1
1.5%	Cowpea	520.0	343.1	52.0	5.2	160.8	110.7
	Waterhyacinth	434.8	257.9	23.4	-23.4	3.1	-54.9
	Dhaincha	368.4	391.5	78.0	31.2	43.7	-14.3
2.0%	Cowpea	416.7	289.8	67.2	20.4	195.3	137.3
	Waterhyacinth	439.7	262.3	20.8	-26.0	15.5	-42.5
	Dhaincha	453.0	276.3	34.6	17.8	6.2	-51.8
2.5%	Cowpea	606.0	429.1	75.5	28.7	217.5	159.5
	Waterhyacinth	469.0	292.1	33.8	-13.0	21.9	-36.1
	Dhaincha	606.0	429.1	56.0	9.2	6.2	-51.8

A= Available S/Available N/O mineralised in mg/100 g of soil.
B= Increase over control in mg/100 g soil.

In calculating the overall effect of added organic materials in the soil, the results of analysis of the soil not treated with organic matter were subtracted from those of soil plus organic matter.

Results and Discussion

Irrespective of the nature of the added plant materials, carbon mineralisation increased with the increase in their amounts (Table 1). But the rate of CO_2 evolution followed the order: dhaincha > cowpea >> water-hyacinth, which is also the order of their initial carbon contents. In order to have a closer look at the increases of CO_2 production the increments for each 0.5% (w/w) in different ranges of addition were computed. The increment was higher in the 0-0.5% range than in the other ranges computed (Table 2) in the case of dhaincha and cowpea. But in the case of water-hyacinth the increase was maximum in the range of 0.5 to 1.0%. No explanations are forthcoming at this stage of investigation.

 TABLE 2—THE RELATIONSHIP OF ADDED INCREMENTS OF DIFFERENT LEVELS OF PLANT MATERIALS TO INCREASE IN THE PRODUCTION OF CO_2 AND AVAILABLE N AND S IN THE SOIL

Nature of added plant material		Mineralisation of C, N and S (mg/100 g) per 0.5% increase in the level of plant material addition				
		0-0.5%	0.5-1.0%	1.0-1.5%	1.5-2.0%	2.0-2.5%
Cowpea	C	210.7	43.9	88.5	—	—
	N	- 5.2	10.4	0	15.2	8.3
	S	-51.8	28.1	134.4	26.6	22.2
Dhaincha	C	257.1	32.8	102.0	—	—
	N	5.2	44.3	-18.3	-13.4	-8.6
	S	-33.0	3.9	14.8	-37.5	0
Water-hyacinth	C	57.1	123.3	77.5	4.9	29.3
	N	-13.0	0	-10.4	-12.6	13.0
	S	—	—	0	12.4	6.4

Although the highest value of available nitrogen (2 M KCl extractable $\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$) was observed in the dhaincha treatment (96.3 mg/100 g at 1% level

of addition) and the least in the water-hyacinth treatment (33.8 mg/100 g at 1% level), the difference in the amount of available nitrogen between the treated soil and untreated control tends to rise upto 2.5% level in the cowpea added soil (28.7 mg/100 g) but upto 1% level in the dhaincha treated soil (49.5 mg/100 g) (Table 1), whereas, immobilisation of available nitrogen was noted in the water-hyacinth treated soil. However, possibility of some amount of denitrification loss from the soil cannot be excluded. The quantity of nitrogen mineralised from the added organic matter in soil during decomposition obviously is mainly a function of the chemical nature and amount of organic matter and the degree of microbial activity. The results shown in Table 2 support this contention. Since nitrogen mineralisation is largely influenced by C/N ratio of the added organic matter it is pertinent to view the results in terms of this ratio. Thus C/N ratio of dhaincha sample was the least (10.0) and that of water-hyacinth the highest (14.9), cowpea being intermediate between the two (12.8). The order of reactivity is also in this order.

Analysis of 0.15% CaCl_2 extractable sulphate sulphur shows a trend similar to nitrogen. Available sulphate sulphur content of the soil increased with increasing amount of cowpea addition, i.e., from 6.2 mg/100 g at 5% level to 217.5 mg/100 g at the 2.5% level of addition, the maximum increase being observed (Table 2) between 1 and 1.5% level (34.3 to 160.8 mg/100 g). But in dhaincha treated soil a similar trend was expressed only upto 1.5% level of addition. In the water-hyacinth treatment, the highest value of available sulphate sulphur was observed at the 0.5% level of addition (78.6 mg/100 g) which sharply decreased to 3.1 mg/100 g at 1% and 1.5% level of addition.

Sulphur mineralisation, it appeared, was not only dependent on the sulphur content of the added plant material but also on C/S and N/S ratios. Similar conclusions were reported by Barrow⁶.

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